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RESEARCH PAPER

CORRELATION BETWEEN FOREARM LENGTH AND FOOT LENGTH AMONG STUDENTS OF AHMADU BELLO UNIVERSITY, ZARIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the correlation between forearm and foot lengths among 490 healthy students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria, aged 18–29 years. Using standardized anthropometric techniques, their right and left forearm and foot lengths, as well as height (m), weight (kg) and BMI (kg/m²) were measured. Data analysis was performed using IBM SPSS version 22. Results showed that males had significantly higher values for all measurements except BMI, where females had higher mean value ($p < 0.05$). A strong statistical correlation was observed between right forearm length (RFL) and the left foot length (LFtL) ($r = 0.582$), suggesting that forearm length may be a reliable predictor of foot length, particularly in males. These findings have forensic applications, aiding in victim identification through body proportion analysis. Additionally, they hold practical value in clinical evaluations, industrial design, medical device development, foot-ware production and workspace optimization. However, the study is limited by its focus on specific age group and population, restricting generalizability. Future research should explore these correlations across broader demographics to enhance applicability.

Keywords: Forearm length, Foot length, Students, Forensic Identification, Ergonomics, Regression Analysis

INTRODUCTION

Forensic anthropology plays a pivotal role in identifying skeletal remains, especially in cases involving mass disasters, criminal scenes, or unidentified human remains, particularly in cases involving mass disasters, crime scenes, or unidentified human remains. Stature estimation is a fundamental aspect of forensic investigations, as it aids in reconstructing an individual's biological profile (Choong *et al.*, 2020). However, direct height measurements are often impossible, necessitating the use of other anthropometric markers, such as proportional limb measurements for identification (Kulkarni & SC, 2021).

The estimation of stature based on body proportions, including forearm and foot length, has proven valuable in forensic investigations, ergonomic applications, and medical evaluations. Earlier studies have highlighted the significance of

these measurements in biomechanics, prosthetic development, and forensic anthropology (Shen *et al.*, 2023; Jouzdani *et al.*, 2022; Pooja & Naqvi, 2020).

Numerous studies have explored stature estimation using upper and lower limb measurement. However, their findings are often based non-African populations, limiting their applicability to Nigerian populations (Bal and Bapuli, 2022; Ugowe *et al.*, 2022). Despite the well-established relationship between limb measurements and stature, the correlation between forearm length and foot length remains understudied, particularly among Nigerian university students. Given the importance of anthropometric data in forensic science, clinical evaluation, and ergonomic design, region-specific studies are essential for establishing localized anthropometric standards.

This research aims to examine the correlation between forearm length and foot length among students at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria. By analyzing potential sexual dimorphism in these measurements, this study seeks to develop anthropometric guidelines relevant to forensic identification, biomechanics, and ergonomic applications. The findings will enhance understanding of the anthropometric characteristics of the Nigerian University student population and provide basis for practical applications in forensic and medical fields.

METHODOLOGY

Study Site and Study Design: This 14-day cross-sectional study was conducted among Ahmadu Bello University (ABU) students, Zaria. A self-administered paper questionnaire was distributed to 490 students, comprising 299 males and females, aged between 18 and 29 years, alongside required measurement protocols.

Ethical Consideration: Ethical approval for research was obtained from Ahmadu Bello University Research Ethics Committee. Informed consent form was obtained from all participants before data collection, and they were given the option to withdraw at any time. The study procedures were fully explained to the participants, emphasizing voluntarily participation. All participants' information was kept strictly confidential.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Healthy students aged 18 to 29 years with no evident skeletal deformities and a willingness to participate was included in this study. Individuals outside the specified age range and those with a history of forearm or foot injuries, surgeries, or chronic conditions that could affect natural body proportions, even in the absence of visible skeletal deformities, were excluded.

Sampling Technique: A random sampling technique was adopted to ensure fairness in participants' selection. Thus, to enhance sample representativeness, students were randomly selected from various faculties. Potential biases, such as the over-representation of students willing to participate or measurement errors were considered. These biases were minimized through randomization and standardized measurement procedures.

Measurements: All the measurements were conducted under well-lit conditions using standard anthropometric equipment and recorded to two decimal places. To ensure reliability, two trained examiners independently took measurements. Agreement between their readings was assessed, and discrepancies were resolved through logical discussion.

- 1. Foot Length Measurements:** All measurements were taken with participants in a standing position. Each participant placed their foot horizontally on the foot measurer, ensuring the heel was positioned against the posterior border of the devise. The adjustable ruler was then placed at the tip of the toes in a manner described by Iroanya *et al.* (2020).

2. **Forearm Length:** This was done using a standard measuring tape. Measurements were taken with the forearm flexed, from the tip of the olecranon process to the midpoint between the radius and ulnar tuberosity as described by Asiwe *et al.*, 2024).
3. **Height:** Participants’ height was measured using a digital stadiometer, the height was determined by measuring the head at the Frankfurt level using a stadiometer while standing barefooted and recorded in meters (Musa & Musa, 2022)
4. **Weight:** The participants’ weight was measured using digital weighing scale while in standing barefoot and wearing light cotton clothing as described by Musa and Musa (2022).
5. **Body Mass Index (BMI):** Body Mass Index (BMI) was calculated by dividing participants' weights in kg by the square of their heights in m². The final BMI values were expressed in kg/m² (Khanna *et al.*, 2022).

Data Analysis: The data analysis section of this study examines the correlation between forearm length and foot length among students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, using statistical methods. Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation were used to summarize findings. Pearson’s correlation coefficient was employed to determine the strength and direction of the association between the two variables. Regression analysis equation was used to estimate foot length from forearm length.

RESULTS

Comparison of Anthropometric Parameters of Male and Female Subjects in the Study.

Table 2 presents a comparison of anthropometric parameters between male and female participants. It shows that the males had significantly higher mean values for forearm length, foot length, and height compared to females. However, there was no significant difference in weight between the sexes. In contrast, females had a significantly higher BMI than males. These findings highlight the presence of sexual dimorphism in body proportions among the study population.

Table 1: Anthropometric Measurements and Comparison in Male and Female Students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

Parameters	Males (n=299)	Females (n=191)	t	p-value
Age (yrs.)	23.15±2.272	22.13±2.025	5.077	<0.0001*
RFL (cm)	28.22±1.724	27.52±1.561	4.608	<0.0001*
LFL (cm)	28.34±1.788	27.53±1.620	5.072	<0.0001*
RFtL (cm)	26.26±1.416	25.03±1.513	9.138	<0.0001*
LFtL(cm)	26.32±1.405	25.03±1.513	10.095	<0.0001*
Ht (m)	1.70±0.074	1.64±0.054	11.678	<0.0001*
Wt. (kg)	63.02±9.474	62.56±12.362	0.438	0.661
BMI (kg/m ²)	21.73±3.093	23.37±4.357*	-4.513	<0.0001*

RFL: right forearm length; LFL: left forearm length; RFtL: right foot length; LFtL: left foot length; Ht: height; Wt: weight; BMI: body mass index; *p<0.05(indicate statistical significance, insignificant values are unmarked).

Correlation Matrix of the Anthropometric Parameter used among the subjects.

Table 2 presents the Pearson correlation coefficients among selected anthropometric parameters. The results indicate a strong positive correlation between right and left forearm lengths, and between the right and left foot lengths. Forearm and foot lengths also show moderate correlations with height. Additionally, weight and BMI exhibit a strong positive correlation. However, BMI shows a weak negative correlation with height, suggesting that taller individuals tend to have lower BMI values within this study population. These findings highlight key relationships among body proportions,

Table 2: Pearson correlation coefficients among selected anthropometric parameters.

Parameters	Age (yrs.)	RFL (cm)	LFL (cm)	RFtL (cm)	LFtL (cm)	Ht (m)	Wt (kg)	BMI (kg/m ²)
Age (yrs.)	1	.087	.158	.132	.114	.089	.203	.166
RFL (cm)		1	.944	.578	.582	.656	.276	-.065
LFL (cm)			1	.566	.578	.653	.276	-.064
RFtL (cm)				1	.973	.740	.392	.017
LFtL (cm)					1	.740	.362	-.015
Ht (m)						1	.359	-.171
Wt. (kg)							1	.855
BMI (kg/m ²)								1

RFL: right forearm length; LFL: left forearm length; RFtL: right foot length; LFtL: left foot length; Ht: height; Wt: weight; BMI: body mass index.

Estimation of Foot Length from Forearm Length

Male Participants

The linear regression equation for estimating foot length from forearm length for the sample population. The Pearson’s coefficient of regression (R), coefficient of determination (R²), and standard error of the estimate (SEE) were also depicted. The regression model revealed the relationship between the outcome and explanatory variables. RFL and LFL for the prediction of RFtL and LFtL in males yielded coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.377 accounting for 37.7%, 0.333 accounting for 33.3% and 0.374 accounting for 37.4% and 0.338 accounting for 33.8% of the dependent variables respectively i.e., males’ foot (right and left) is predicted by the independent variables (Table 4).

Table 4: Regression equations for estimating foot length from forearm length in male students.

Predictors	Predictive Equation	R	R ²	SEE	P
RFL	RFtL (cm) = 12.02+(0.505) X RFL	0.614	0.377	1.11983	<0.0001
LFL	RFL (cm) = 13.302+(0.457) X LFL	0.557	0.333	1.15836	<0.0001
RFL	LFtL (cm) = 12.253+(0.498) X RFL	0.611	0.374	1.11379	<0.0001
LFL	LFtL (cm) = 13.368+(0.457) X LFL	0.582	0.338	1.14478	<0.0001

RFL: right forearm length; LFL: left forearm length; RFtL: right foot length; LFtL: left foot length; Ht: height; Wt: weight; BMI: body mass index; SEE: standard error of the estimate; R: Pearson’s coefficient of correlation; R²: coefficient of determination.

Female Participants

The RFL and LFL for the prediction of RFtL in females also yielded coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.210 accounting for 21% and 0.218 accounting for 21.8% and 0.246 accounting for 24.6% of the dependent variables respectively i.e., females' foot (right and left) is predicted by the independent variables (table 5).

Table 4: Regression equations for estimating foot length from forearm length in female students.

Predictors	Predictive Equation	R	R^2	SEE	P
RFL	RFtL (cm) = 12.815+(0.444) X RFL	0.458	0.210	1.34835	<0.0001
LFL	RFL (cm) = 13.039+(0.436) X LFL	0.466	0.218	1.34162	<0.0001
RFL	LFtL (cm) = 12.334+(0.459) X RFL	0.477	0.228	1.3225	<0.0001
LFL	LFtL (cm) = 12.328+(0.459) X LFL	0.496	0.246	1.30701	<0.0001

RFL: right forearm length; LFL: left forearm length; RFtL: right foot length; LFtL: left foot length; Ht: height; Wt: weight; BMI: body mass index; SEE: standard error of the estimate; R: Pearson's coefficient of correlation; R^2 : coefficient of determination.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study are consistent with previous research highlighting the importance of foot and forearm measurements in forensic identification, sports biomechanics, and anthropometric modeling. With the differences in the length of the foot and length of the forearm observed in this study of the participants being in agreement with studies done in the past (Agrawal *et al.*, 2023; Ugowe *et al.*, 2022) where men generally have longer limb proportions than women. Our results suggest that males possess distinctly longer forearms and feet than females, in contrast to a higher BMI in females, which is characteristic of several populations examined.

A key finding of our study is the moderate-to-strong correlation ($r \geq 0.578$) between forearm length and foot length, indicating that forearm measurement can serve as a useful proxy for estimating foot dimensions when direct measurement cannot be performed. This is especially prominent in forensic anthropology where the identification process often involves reconstructing the missing parts of the remains. Our findings confirmed those by Bal and Bapuli (2022) who found forearm length to be a significant predictor of height. Yet, although Bal and Bapuli (2022) presented characteristics for stature estimation, our study widens the horizons of this approach by validating the forearm-foot length relationship, a new anthropometric correlation applied to forensic and medical sciences.

Additionally, Agrawal *et al.* (2023) reported clinically significant differences in foot morphology and arch height based on sex and recommended sex and ankle joint-specific anthropometric measurements models to potentially facilitate rehabilitation. Our results support this view; we found substantial sex differences in foot length, and forearm-foot length relations were more predictive in males ($R^2 = 33.3\% - 37.7\%$) than in females ($R^2 = 21.0\% - 24.6\%$). These results indicate that for various forensic and medical applications, separate regression models for males and females may more accurately estimate the relevant traits.

Aside from their forensic applications, our results may have implications in sports biomechanics. Manzi *et al.* (2023) examined the influence of forearm pronation and foot structure on athletic performance, particularly in relation to biomechanical efficiency and injury prevention. While our study did not directly assess biomechanical function, the correlation between forearm and foot length may provide valuable insights for athletic performance assessments, rehabilitation programs, and ergonomic designs for athletes. Future studies could explore whether these anthropometric relationships influence balance, gait mechanics, or sports-related injuries

Despite these results, our study has notable limitations. The availability of respondents that belong to the university student population in the age group of 18–29, limited generalizability our findings to any other age groups or work

backgrounds. For example, anthropometric associations can differ when accounting for ethnicity, activity levels, and genetic influences, and thus these factors were not controlled for. Future studies are welcomed with larger and diverse cohorts, as well as advanced measurement technologies such as 3D imaging or machine learning-based predictive models to overcome these shortcomings.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the strong relationship between forearm and foot lengths, showing its practical in application and benefits in forensic identification systems as well as medical diagnostics services and ergonomic product development. The findings indicate gender disparities, with males exhibiting stronger predictive relationships than females, emphasizing the need for distinct anthropometric models by sex. The study has practical value in clinical evaluations and industrial design work which leads toward patient-centered medical devices, footwear development and workspace optimization. However, the study is limited by its focus on specific age group and population, which may limit the generalizability of the result to other age group. Future research should explore these relationships across more diverse demographics to enhance generalizability.

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AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTION

Sample collection and data analysis was conducted by Bello J. O. and Musa I. O. The initial manuscript draft was prepared by Bello J. O., Aliyu I. A., and Musa I. O. The final manuscript draft was facilitated by Okon J. E., Adebisi A. O., Abimbola A. J., Olawoye F. B., Ahmad A. M., Oladipupo L. O., Abdulrauf A., and Muhammad H.

